

The power of photosynthesis

Plants and algae belong to the most important organisms on Earth, fixing energy from sunlight and producing biomass from carbon dioxide and water. The underlying biological process – photosynthesis – not only secures food but also energy supply by converting carbon dioxide into sugar molecules that allow plants to develop and grow. It also supplies, as a by-product, oxygen, the most important gas vital for breathing organisms. Thus, photosynthesis influences the development of ecosystems and affects the balance between oxygen and carbon dioxide, and hence the composition of the atmosphere.

Unravelling the secrets of photosynthesis is therefore of crucial importance for maintaining plant biomass supply for humankind and as a key process that helps to counteract (human-induced) climate change.

GoFORSYS, a BMBF-funded Research Unit on Systems Biology in Potsdam-Golm

Thanks to substantial financial support by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), the Systems Biology Centre GoFORSYS could be established in 2007 in Potsdam-Golm, close to Germany's capital Berlin. It develops under the wider umbrella of the 'FORSYS – Research Units for Systems Biology', launched to build interdisciplinary, collaborative and internationally recognised units for Systems Biology at universities, non-profit research institutions and industrial companies in Germany.

In GoFORSYS, scientists study the activity of genes and the dynamic changes of metabolites and proteins in a green algal model (called

Chlamydomonas reinhardtii) in response to environmental factors that affect photosynthesis. In addition, emphasis is given to the analysis of photosynthesis in the model plant *Arabidopsis thaliana* (more commonly called thale cress) and the important crop tomato.

GoFORSYS is a collaborative initiative of the University of Potsdam's Institute of Biochemistry and Biology, the Max Planck Institute of Molecular Plant Physiology and the Max Planck Institute of Colloids and Interfaces. All three are located in close vicinity at the Science Park in Potsdam-Golm. 17 academic partners with expertise in biology, biochemistry, chemistry, computational biology, theoretical physics, and mathematics collaborate within GoFORSYS. An industrial partner complements the available spectrum of technologies and links Systems Biology to applied plant research.

Teaching in Systems Biology

The GoFORSYS research is based on an intensive exchange between experiment and theory, and – in particular – it builds upon young scientists well trained in both fields.

Investigation of regulatory networks in plant metabolism: from genomics to product innovation...

While in the past students were often either educated in experimental science or bio-computational methods, the courses of study offered now in the frame of the GoFORSYS programme strongly emphasise an interdisciplinary approach.

Within the GoFORSYS PhD programme, new supervision schemes and organisational structures were implemented to widen training output and support career development. Furthermore, strong links exist to an International Max Planck Research School (IMPRS) on plant primary metabolism and growth. Notably, 30 GoFORSYS doctoral students have already successfully concluded their PhD theses by the end of 2010. In addition, the university has established a Master's of Science programme in Bioinformatics with a particular focus on Systems Biology.

Systems Biology to study photosynthesis

Photosynthesis is a complex physiological process that in land plants and many green algae occurs in cellular compartments called chloroplasts. However, photosynthetic reactions do not run in isolation,

Crop development and growth under controlled conditions

rather they are intermingled with many other physiological processes. Similarly, the building of chloroplasts during plant development is a highly regulated process not well understood today.

If we were to understand growth and biomass accumulation in plants – and finally yield – we have to unravel the underlying molecular processes and learn how they interact and influence each other during growth. Systems Biology offers the best way to exactly do this. Breeding and genetic engineering will then help to make use of the newly gained knowledge to adjust plants to our needs, as in centuries before.

The term 'Systems Biology' was coined a decade ago to highlight a new research direction in biology that aims at analysing the complex molecular, biochemical and physiological interactions in cells, organs and entire organisms. Systems Biology relies on the rapid development of a diverse and complementary spectrum of high-throughput analysis technologies that allow researchers to look deeply into numerous cellular activities at the gene, protein and metabolite levels.

Systems Biology researchers take these large-scale (often dubbed 'omics') datasets to carefully analyse them with the help of powerful computational and mathematical tools. Finally, mathematical models are formulated to describe the dynamic behaviour of the cellular activities. The newly gained knowledge is then used to design further wet-lab

experiments that help to validate (or disprove) the models. Evidently, in Systems Biology wet-lab researchers have to cooperate closely and constantly with computational experts to advance understanding about how cell components interact to establish life.

The members of the GoFORSYS consortium initially focus on a relatively simple photosynthetic organism, the green alga

Chlamydomonas reinhardtii, to study the impact of changing environmental conditions on gene expression, cell metabolism and growth. In the second phase of the research programme results are compared with those gained through the analysis of more complex plants like thale cress and tomato.

Environmental factors are chosen by identifying important constraints on photosynthesis and productivity in crops, which can also be studied in the model algal species. This includes the interactions between light intensity, light quality and temperature, all of which are known to affect photosynthetic electron transport and metabolism. Furthermore, the researchers investigate the impact of nitrogen availability on photosynthesis, as it is another key element controlling plant growth.

The future of Systems Biology in Potsdam

Undoubtedly, GoFORSYS enabled the University of Potsdam and the Max Planck Institutes on campus to jointly develop a strong focus on Systems Biology, very much to the benefit of our young biology students. In this vein, the university established a new focus area in 2009 – Plant Genomics and Systems Biology – and appointed a full professor for Mathematical Modelling and Systems Biology in 2010. Two further appointments in support of plant-oriented ('green') Systems Biology are currently ongoing, one focusing on metabolism, the other on physiology. In addition, the Max Planck Institute of Molecular Plant

Physiology will establish a cluster of independent research groups working in the field of Systems Biology.

Meanwhile, GoFORSYS has been established as a competence centre for 'green' Systems Biology that, for example, is reflected by the fact that already four young group leaders were offered calls to university chairs in Scotland, Austria and Germany. A further indicator for this is the increased interest of industry and EU consortia to apply systems approaches in conjunction with GoFORSYS researchers.

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